

SITE GPR	YEAR 2012	AREA F	SECTOR	ELEVATION Min 62.5056 Max 63.5255	STRATIGRAPHICAL UNIT 5016 ☐ Natural ☒ Anthropogenic	Gabilan
In cross-section? ☒ Yes ☐ No		In elevation drawing? ☐ Yes ☒ No		Photos: ☒ Yes ☐ No #: 2490-2495		Photo Model: ☐ Yes ☒ No #:
DEFINITION Fill of construction cut wall 5018			Covered by ☒ SU: 0	Fills ☒ SU: 5017	Filled by ☐ SU:	
HOW IS LAYER DISTINGUISHED? ☐ Color ☒ Composition ☐ Compaction			FORMATION PROCESS ☐ Accumulation ☐ Construction ☐ Cutting ☐ Erosion ☐ Collapse ☒ Intentional deposition			
INCLUSIONS For each inclusion specify frequency: (f) frequent, (m) medium, (r) rare			SOIL/MATRIX clay 2% silt 90% sand 8%			
Anthropic		Geological		Organic		
☒ Pottery f ☒ Tiles f ☒ Amphorae (m) ☐ Dolia ☒ Mosaic tile(s) r ☐ Mortar ☐ Coins ☒ Metal (specify) f ☐ Collapse debris ☒ Glass r		☒ Tuff (specify) (f) ☐ Travertine ☐ Other Limestone ☒ Basalt r ☐ Clay ☐ Sand ☐ Silt ☐ Pebbles (range) ☐ Gravel (range) ☒ Iron nails, necessaries, Flint - r ☒ sandstone - r		☒ Charcoal f ☐ Ash ☐ Animal bones f ☐ Human bones ☒ Animal teeth m ☐ Human teeth ☒ Shells m ☐ Other (specify)		
			Compaction ☐ Hard ☐ Compact ☒ Friable ☐ Loose ☐ Soft		Color ☐ Black ☐ Brown ☐ Gray ☒ Light Brown ☐ Light Gray ☐ White ☐ Yellow ☐ Red ☐ Light Yellow ☐ Other (specify)	

UNIT LIMITS (also indicate on overlay)

Northern Limit	☒ Original ☐ Not Original ☐ Excavation Limit	Depth: ☐ Original ☒ Not Original
Southern Limit	☐ Original ☐ Not Original ☒ Excavation Limit	
Western Limit	☒ Original ☐ Not Original ☐ Excavation Limit	
Eastern Limit	☒ Original ☐ Not Original ☐ Excavation Limit	

STRATIGRAPHICAL SEQUENCE

Is equal to:	Is bound to (only for masonry):
Is abutted by:	Abuts:
Is covered by: SU 0	Covers:
Is cut by:	Cuts:
Is filled by:	Fills: 5017

OBSERVATIONS
Excavated on dry/sunny day w/ good visibility with pickaxe & shovel. SU is truncated in south by 2012 Area F Excavation Limit. Δ 713-722; Δ 724-726 found throughout (mostly in southern end)

DESCRIPTION
Position within sector: along south-eastern Area F excavation limit (along wall SU 5018)
Shape: long rectangle

For layers complete this section:
Surface (slope direction, visible inclusions): slopes down slightly south w/ large step down toward S - south in center; Pottery, tiles + animal bones visible on surface
Observations about inclusions (Clusters? Deposition slope): special finds mostly southern half, animals concentrated in center and south in northern part! Deposition deeper in south end.
Observations about thickness (Increases? Decreases?): thicker on northern half before step
Nature of the interface with layer below: sharp diffuse commingled other (specify)

- Δ 713 - Bronze Stylus
 - Δ 714 - Lamp
 - Δ 715 - "Gladiator" Lamp
 - Δ 716 - Bronze lip
 - Δ 717 - bronze object (tweezers)
 - Δ 718 - BRONZE TIN
 - Δ 719 - Lamp Fragment
 - Δ 720 - miniature vessel
 - Δ 721 weight (beard?)
 - Δ 722 lamp (diver?)
 - Δ 724 iron attachment
 - Δ 725 bone object
 - Δ 726 BONE HAIR PIN
- (we do go back to top)

For structural remains complete this section

Alignment:

Building Technique: Adobe/Mud-brick Ashlar (blocks) irregular (unworked) stone Concrete Other (specify)

Binding Agent: None Clay Mortar (if so, specify composition, color, compaction)

Concrete inclusions:

Material Tufo Basalt Travertine Tiles Other (specify)

Size Small (range) _____ Medium (range) _____ Large (range) _____ Representative size, e.g. 2 x 1 x 2 cm

Wall Facing:

Opus quadratum Opus incertum Opus reticulatum Petit appareil Opus testaceum Opus mixtum Opus vittatum Other (specify)

Complete this section for foundations Faced foundation Wooden shuttering No shuttering

Floor/revetment type

Floor type: Beaten Earth Opus signinum Opus scutulatum Opus Sectile Mosaic Opus spicatum Other (specify)

Wall finishing Stucco Opus signinum Plaster Painted Plaster Other (specify)

Approx. length, width, height of structural remains:

Description:

Sketch (if applicable, indicate North)

INTERPRETATION

SU 5016 contained many large animal bones, a variety of pottery, including several micelamps, tiles, shells, lead, bronze and a lot of iron nails + fragments as well as special finds Δ713-722; Δ724-726. Due to the large variety + quantity of material found in SU 5016 it appears that this was a fill for a construction cut (SU 5017) of wall 5018. This fill seems to indicate a later phase of wall construction as it does not continue to the lower course of the wall.

SOIL SAMPLING: Yes No

Total volume of layer (buckets):

Sample quantity (buckets):

Sample fraction (%):

NON SOIL SAMPLES: Yes No

If yes, specify (e.g. charcoal, mortar etc.):

CHARCOAL

Size: SMALL

SIEVING: Yes No

Total volume of layer (buckets):

Sample quantity (buckets):

Sample fraction (%):

STRATIGRAPHICAL RELIABILITY

Good Fair Poor

Filled-out by: SJ, KH, KC, BJ, EK

on: July 28th 2012

Revised by: CH

on: 11.7.2012

PDF'd by: GP

on: 12.7.2012

Entered by:

on: